

SPECIFICITY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS WITH PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The proverb provides an analysis of theoretical and practical information regarding the specific aspects of interpersonal relationships among primary school students. In particular, the content of the scientific approaches and views of foreign scholars on interpersonal relations in the collective of primary school students is described. Research has also been conducted on the study of interpersonal relationships among primary school students.

Keywords: primary school age, interpersonal relations, interaction, leader, external factor, internal factor, cooperation, conflict, competition, self-awareness, autonomy, attitude toward others, human perception.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ МЕЖЛИЧНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ УЧАЩИХСЯ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация. В пословице представлен анализ теоретических и практических сведений об особенностях межличностных отношений учащихся младшего школьного возраста. В частности, изложено содержание научных подходов и взглядов зарубежных ученых на межличностные отношения в коллективе учащихся младшего школьного возраста. Также были проведены исследования по изучению межличностных отношений у учащихся младшего школьного возраста.

Ключевые слова: младший школьный возраст, межличностные отношения, взаимоотношения, лидер, внешний фактор, внутренний фактор, сотрудничество, конфликт, конкуренция, самосознание, автономия, отношение к окружающим людям, восприятие человека человеком.

The experience of interpersonal relationships with other people, adults, or peers serves as a foundation for the development of a child's personality and the formation of their self-awareness. How easily a child will be able to communicate with the people around them and establish contact depends on their further educational and work activities, as well as their fate and place in life. Especially relevant is the study of interpersonal relationship features in the early school age, as it is during this period that personality formation occurs and the need arises for a deeper psychological-pedagogical study of the child and their diverse contacts with adults and peers.

Primary school age is a special period in a child's life that has emerged relatively recently in age psychology. It is most deeply and meaningfully presented in the works of D. B. Elkonin, V. V. Davidov, and their employees and followers (L. I. Aidarova, A. K. Dusavitsky, A. K. Markova, Yu. A. Poluyanov, V. V. Repin, V. V. Rubtsov, G. A. Tsukerman, etc.).

Thus, the primary school age is the age of 6 (7) -10-year-old children studying in grades 1-4 of modern primary school. With the child's arrival at school, as D. B. Elkonin wrote [6; c. 88], the entire system of the child's relationship with reality is restructured.

At the age of 6, there is a kind of tension and excitement caused by the initial contact with school and the effort to adapt to a new environment. If adaptation to school proceeds well, after the age of 7, the child enters a period of relative calm, adaptation to changes proceeds quite satisfactorily, and the child, rather, internally experiences all types of daily events.

This inner anxiety provokes the child's curiosity, which has a beneficial effect on expanding relationships with the surrounding world. By the age of 9, obvious new opportunities for self-awareness and autonomy appear, and therefore the child becomes more orderly, more serious, and even feels the need to organize their time. By the age of 10, a child reaches a kind of peak of childhood, manifesting in the ability to quickly navigate school life, solve school problems, understand various situations, remain calm, control themselves, and restrain emotional reactions [1, 6].

Acquiring social interaction skills with a group of peers and the ability to make friends is one of the most important tasks in a child's development at this age stage [1]. During the early school years, new types of relationships are formed based on the fact that school, as a social institution, consists of classes—collectives of children of equal age and undergoing the same education—which creates a strong competitive spirit [2].

In school, according to D. B. Elkonin [6; c. 94], a new structure of these relations arises. The "child-adult" system is differentiated into: child-teacher and child-parents. The most important system for developing a child's self-awareness is the "child-teacher" system. The teacher not only teaches children various subjects and reveals many interesting things about the world around them, but also influences the formation of the child's understanding of themselves and their abilities, as well as determines the child's attitude toward parents and their attitude toward children. The "child-teacher" system becomes the center of a child's life, and the sum of all favorable conditions for life depends on it.

It is important to note that the process of developing interpersonal relationships is most influenced by the teacher's educational influence, which can also serve as a criterion for analyzing interactions in the classroom:

- cooperation relations: based on the coordination of efforts to achieve a common goal,
- competitive relations: competition in achieving individual goals,
- conflict relations: opposition relations in achieving individual goals.

Morton noted that in classes with a competitive atmosphere, children have a high level of anxiety, children think less about themselves and their affairs, are prejudiced against their classmates, and exhibit a low level of responsibility. Deutsch studied the phenomena of competition and cooperation in children's collectives 35 years ago, leading to an important conclusion for teachers: the more children participate in activities that require cooperation, the better the overall atmosphere in the classroom will be.

The development of various interests in the specialized role of the cooperative system, increasing favoritism, can lead to discrimination against team members who are not part of the group, and the growth of excessive conformity in the absence of majority opinion [7].

Educational influence can be defined as an organizational and structured form of the educational process aimed at the student to form and develop their behavior, attitudes, etc. In this case, educational influence can be analyzed from two perspectives:

- external factor: the teacher's personal influence as a leader;
- internal factor: the influence of a group that regulates formal and informal processes within the class.

The teacher's personal influence is defined as the ability to influence the behavior of other people at every moment of teacher-student interaction. The success of a teacher's educational influence depends on four factors: the characteristics of the emotional relationship established between the teacher and the students; the perception of the teacher by the students; the degree of the teacher's use of power; and the degree of individualization of the work strategies used by the teacher [4].

Class, as a school form of social organization for children, exerts an increasing influence on the child's development, helping them master new rules, social norms, and value orientations. In the classroom, the child develops communication skills, gains experience in collective activities, develops self-esteem, and gains the opportunity for personal self-affirmation. However, it should be noted that creating and uniting the class collective is one of the primary tasks of the teacher.

Communication with peers plays an important role at this age, as it not only helps children socialize in new conditions and stimulates their learning but also contributes to the formation of adequate self-esteem.

The self-esteem and self-knowledge of primary school students are formed through communication with peers, and the child perceives themselves through the prism of the collective as an integral part of the community. Children's assessment of their peers is linked to the level of development of optimism, kindness, sincerity, and reflection on their own behavior. Children who exhibit less adequate behavior and exhibit impatience, anger, and resentment, as a rule, find it more difficult to establish interpersonal relationships and are less sociable. Adults participating in the educational process are the only factor capable of helping such children establish and establish relationships with the collective in the classroom. First- and second-grade children do not yet possess sufficiently developed moral and ethical judgments, cannot independently evaluate a particular form of behavior, and are most often oriented toward the opinions of adults. For children of this age, the teacher's personality is a model to be imitated, which is why the teacher must act as an initiator of communication and support the interpersonal interaction of children. It is in the lower grades that the foundations of independent thinking and personal autonomy are laid, as well as the ability to form and defend one's point of view and make choices. However, such personality formation is possible only in a collective where the teacher models and maintains proper behavior.

A young child's character develops because the social situation itself (school and class) daily models new situations, places the child in new circumstances, and provides them with the opportunity to see, participate in, and analyze various cases, forms of behavior, etc. Life in a collective helps a child develop moral behavior and feelings such as responsibility, honesty, selflessness, sincerity, mutual assistance, and solidarity. From this, we conclude that it is the educational process that forms the basis of character and personality.

Children have different attitudes toward their peers: the student chooses some classmates, does not choose others, and rejects others; the attitude toward some is stable, while toward others it is unstable [3]. In younger school-age children, interest in friends often arises when they want to share their

ideas, interests, when they are sad, or when they do not dare to do something, when they have discovered something new for themselves and feel a need for communication, when they need emotional comfort, and a friend of the same age is an invaluable treasure.

This kind of attitude toward a peer-friend is possible because at this age, children live with the awareness that the "I" has the same characteristics as the "You" (the other). A friend for a child becomes an object of solidarity, trust, and a warm emotional attitude. However, one should not forget the role of the family. It is the benevolent family environment and the love of parents that contribute to a child's positive positioning in school and the formation of adequate self-esteem and corresponding self-awareness. In all types of interpersonal interaction (with parents, in the family, with teachers, with classmates, with peers, etc.), children learn and develop their capacity for self-observation, self-analysis, and self-esteem.

In primary school, relationships with only one friend are quite rare. Most often, children build friendships with colleagues who study well and are role models because they are singled out and praised by the teacher. Children establish friendship relations and teach communication in the same way that adults, relatives, peers, and, of course, the teacher do. Younger schoolchildren have many friends among the class collective, in the yard, in circles, and in the sections they attend. However, it is important for them that these relationships be maintained by adults involved in the children's upbringing. In this regard, it should be noted that in the struggle for a teacher's praise, children struggle with their peers, as they see each other as rivals. For the personality of a primary school student to mature, it is important to learn to perceive peers as colleagues.

Let us note another feature of interpersonal relationships in younger schoolchildren: relations are built on the basis of gender, and moreover, groups of boys and girls at this age may even be at enmity with one another. Separation by sex at this age characterizes not only the composition of groups but also the venues for games and entertainment. At the same time, special "girls" and "boys" places are formed throughout the entire territory of the games, which are not marked externally, but are protected from intrusion by "outsiders" and avoided by them. Interestingly, in the event that boys and girls unite for a common game, a place is chosen for it between two territories [5].

Thus, relationships with other people emerge and develop most intensively during childhood. The experience of these first relationships serves as a foundation for the further development of a child's personality and largely determines the specifics of their attitude toward themselves, others, and the world as a whole. Thus, it can be concluded that interpersonal relationships in primary school age depend on many factors, such as academic success, mutual liking, commonality of interests, external life circumstances, and sexual characteristics. All these factors influence the nature of the child's relationships with others and their significance.

In our research work, a sociometric method was conducted on a group of subjects to study interpersonal relationships within the group. To study students' communication with peers and determine their position in the group, we used a modified form of the sociometric method called "Sociometry." The methodology is aimed at studying issues of interpersonal communication within the group. For this purpose, subjects are presented with a mask drawn on paper that represents a good or bad mood, a desire for dominance and submission.

This methodology was conducted on a group of subjects, and the results were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The results of the quantitative analysis are presented in tables and diagrams.

Table 1

Table view of the results analysis using sociometry methodology

Синалувчилар	Хўрланганлик	Хукмрон-лидерлик
4-синф	36,8	63,2

Analysis of results according to the methodology showed that the humiliation scale is determined by the presence of strong excitability toward external influences. This indicator is also low among 4th-grade students. We can see that they have their own place in society and the collective. This indicator is more important than the child's position (leadership and humiliation) because it indicates the child's satisfaction with their place in the group. When the idea of bullying is put forward, it refers to children who are not afraid of being in a class or group with their peers and prefer to communicate with them at home in the yard.

This option may also be linked to the child's reluctance to engage in active communication and a general lack of interest in socializing with their peers. At the same time, leaders may also be dissatisfied with their positions. In doing so, they strive to occupy a higher position in the group or try to communicate with children who are not subordinate to the leader in another group.

Thus, the so-called "empty" and "active" oppressed appear. They calmly accept their humiliation and do not strive for communication. Dominance among subjects is of priority importance among 4th-grade students according to the leadership scale, which is explained by their satisfaction with collective relationships and their position in interpersonal relationships.

It is also explained by the fact that collective and interpersonal relations are fully formed within them. This is especially important for children who are dissatisfied with their status. Dissatisfaction with one's position is more common in children who strive for dominance. They are not satisfied with simple communication with their peers; they prefer to break off contact rather than submit to them. Instead of correcting children with such movements by assigning them a specific role in the group, it is important to show them the skills of organizing the activities and games of their peers. Children who are not satisfied with their humiliation and who have a submissive character are ready for any form of communication. These children accept help calmly, whereas children in the first group react to such assistance with caution. In most cases, they strive to be independent.

From the results of the methodology, it can be seen that the characteristics of communicating with younger schoolchildren may depend on communication skills and the system of interpersonal relationships. It also depends on the degree of students' satisfaction with their position and their mutual support.

Based on the studied theoretical approaches and the results of the conducted research, it is advisable to formulate the following conclusions:

- The system of an individual's active relationships with the social environment can be one of the main conditions for interpersonal relationships;
- the ability of primary school students to engage in interpersonal relationships is determined by the formation of their communication skills;
- the ability of primary school students to engage in interpersonal relationships is determined by the formation of a sense of mutual respect and trust;
- The development of personality traits in primary school students is determined by their unique place in the system of interpersonal relationships.

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